

Harnessing the Technical Potential of AI, IT and Data Management For Unlocking India's Economic Success Story

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Abstract – India is committed to become a \$ 5 Trillion economy by the year 2027. Reaching such a pivotal point of economic success, demand adequate utilization of all the major resources of our nation with effective policy making. Our prudence to optimally channelize India's demographic dividend along with effective harnessing of the potential's of AI, Information technology as well as data management can help all the economic sectors to contribute in making India, a \$ 5 trillion economy and much beyond. We all are living in the digital world of forth Industrial revolution; where technological innovation keeps on changing so drastically, that nation's all around the world are racing to become tech giant, so as to gain technological advancement and to yield out economic advancement at last. In such a milieu of technology dynamics, it is mandatory for India as well, to harness the potential of AI and Information technology, to sustain our competitive growth. Maintaining digital and technological strength can be a game changer for us to ensure our economic success. Multiple reports had confirmed that AI alone is expected to add \$ 400 billion to India's GDP by 2025. In fact, "National Strategy for Artificial Intelligence #AIFORALL", a June 2018 report by Niti Aayog also recognizes AI as an opportunity and a precursor of greater good i.e. social development and inclusive growth. This research paper will shed light on all the major aspects that how, AI, IT as well as Data Management would particularly become a factor for India's economic success story. The research paper would utilize secondary data sources for this purpose. Like minded newspaper articles, magazine stuff, authentic reports, data analysis and research papers are used to get a broader picture of it.

Keywords: AI, Information Technology, Economic growth, Data Management, India \$ 5 trillion economy, technology.

1. INTRODUCTION

Modern economies are sharing space with digitalization and Industrial Revolution 4.0, therefore we can't imagine to thrive our economy in the absence of technological inputs. This research paper is based on three tech input namely-

Fig -1: Three Input

In this research paper, we will try to put light on how the three technological aspects namely Artificial Intelligence, Information technology and Data Management are impacting the positively and negatively on Indian Economy. What better place we can reach, if we are able to efficiently handle the technical potential of these technical assistance. In the words of Albert Hubbard, “one machine can do the work of fifty ordinary men. No machine can do the work of one extraordinary man”. Technology has the potential to make drastic changes, all we need is the art to use them in the best possible manner. But before we dive deep into this research paper, it is important to clearly understand what these three technologies are all about, and why it is important for India to harness them for writing its economic success story.

1.1 Understanding AI

A simulation of human intelligence is what we called as Artificial Intelligence. It is the intelligence of computers or machines or any gadget that is making our life even easier. AI works by ingesting enormous amount of data, which help it in its intelligence. It is a branch of computer science working to create smart machines. It has two sub-parts, namely Weak AI and Strong AI. The former i.e. the weak AI is the one which can stimulate human intelligence in limited context that too, after much of training and data processing. Whereas Strong AI is the one which can stimulate intelligence like human, on that problems also for whom it has been not trained earlier.

1.2 Present strength of Artificial Intelligence in India

Artificial Intelligence, a branch of computer science program developed to human behavior. The global AI market size was valued at \$ 136.55 billion in 2022. As per the estimate of a Forbes Advisor report, AI will contribute around \$ 15.7 Trillion to the global economy by 2030. AI is in popular demand in India too. In the year 2020, Indian companies were ranked 2nd in adopting AI in the Asia Pacific. Under Ministry of Electronics and Information Technology (MeitY) we have a dedicated national AI portal called INDIAai. Government in fact also launched innovative challenge called YUVAi – Youth for Unnati and Vikas with AI program to inculcate AI understanding to school students particularly of class 8th to 2th. India is also a founding member of the Global Partnership on Artificial Intelligence (GPAI). We had an AI market of around \$ 6.4 billion.

1.3 Understanding IT

Information Technology (IT) is the use of gadgets, devices and computers for accessing, storing, managing and processing the information. It include cloud computing services, network security, digital communication, data mining, data storage, data synchronization, DBMS, software application, machine learning etc. IT is the lifeline of the information age. It is the foundation of modern digital businesses.

1.4 Present strength of Information Technology in India

The IT sector is an extraordinary sector which had so far acted as a thrust to push the Indian economy to reaches new heights. Today we are among the most promising IT hub of the world. According to a report of IBEF (India Brand Equity Foundation), India's IT and business services market is projected to reach US \$ 19.93 by 2023. In the Fiscal Year 2021, India ranked 3rd worldwide with more than 6 lakh cloud experts across all verticals of technology. Currently the IT industry of India contribute 7.4% of India's GDP in the FY 2022. According to Nasscom, (National Association of Software and Service Companies) India's IT industry alone contribute the revenue of US \$ 227 billion in FY22. The IT industry added 2.9 lakh new jobs taking the industry's total workforce count to 54 lakh people in FY 2023.

1.5 Understanding Data Management

It is the handling of data, a precious intangible asset for any business for their decision making. It include the practice of collecting, keeping and using data to help people and organizations make decisions, policies, regulations and strategies. Data management enhance our working capability via improved decisions, better integration and achievement of quality results. The entire work of data management was done by effective IT teams. Data management is a crucial intelligence which will help businesses and government to optimize their decisions, performance, operations & governance, so as to obtain high profits and revenue. It include data warehousing, data preparation, data integration, data transformation, data governance and master data. Data-driven plans are really helpful in meeting our desired objectives on time. Today most of the Data Management systems are synergistic with the AI tools in one way or the other. This will not only help businesses to produce accurate results, but also enable high performance, increased operational efficiencies as well as improved decision making.

1.6 Present strength of Data Management in India

According to a report titled, "Unlocking the potential of India's Data Economy: Practices, Privacy and Governance" by Monitor Deloitte and Omidyar Network India. Digital transformation of economy has led to the creation of enormous data on routine basis. There is an immense prospect of data gathering, data analysis and data based decision making in this digitalized world order. Therefore controlling such a seamless amount of data is itself a challenge for the economies today. Technologies such as generative chatbot ChatGPT, itself capable to generate enormous data by using machine intelligence in our one command. In order to manage such humongous data, either personal data or non-personal data, India need an effective data governance mechanism. In the year 2023, the Government of India has passed 'The Digital Protection Bill' to safeguard digital personal data and honour Citizen's Right to Privacy. Not only this India is also planning to establish National Data Management Office in order to manage non-personal and anonymized data.

2. AN OVERVIEW OF TECHNICAL POTENTIAL OF AI, IT AND DATA MANAGEMENT

In the words of Godfrey Reggio, "It's not that we use technology, we live technology". We all will agree to this very fact that, in this 21st century, especially for the techade now, we are actually living technology in all practical sense. Rarely any business would be there which is out of the boons of technical aids; be that it be any gadget, internet, software, Artificial intelligence, information technology and last but not the least is the Data Management system. Today the businesses are expanding with the assistance of technology as a whole. And the nations; who are able to harness the optimum potential of different forms of technology are making enormous economic success and enjoying the prominence of the geo-political affairs of the world as well. According to the report by Global Finance, "South Korea is the technologically most advance country of the world, followed by United States, Taiwan, Denmark and Switzerland in the first top five positions. The similar report ranked India at the 62nd position out of 65 nations evaluated in total. In the realm of technological world order, Technology is serving as a power booster to push businesses, start-ups and trade; so as to channelize economic prowess of the nation and help them to thrive economically and financially. Today the wars are not about gaining land and wealth, instead the modern wars are fought with the intention to gain economic hegemony of the world order. We all wanted to become economically strong, and technology is the potential weapon to bridge the gap of our reality to expectation.

3. ROLE OF AI, IT AND DATA MANAGEMENT FOR ECONOMIC GROWTH OF INDIA

3.1 Role of AI

An intelligence which is not real or in artificial; which is posed by the machines, is what we called as Artificial Intelligence. Today AI (Artificial Intelligence) is creating a neck to neck competition against HI (Human Intelligence). AI is the future of the technological world around. Almost every nation in the world, is spending millions of dollars to harness the potential of AI. Interestingly, the AI likewise other technologies is available with two sides of the same coin. If AI is a technological blessing to revolutionize the way industries and economies thrive today, at the same time AI is a cause of concern via miscreants' application of it with deep fakes, cybercrimes and cyber thefts. Therefore, it is crucial for the nation's to invest heavily on AI to effectively balance its scope of application. It is definitely the human, who are using AI in Healthcare, Defense, E-commerce, Education, Gaming, Social Media, Agriculture, Transportation, Robotics and other disciplines. It is we the humans who are using AI at the same time we are using AI for manipulating facts, spreading misinformation, privacy theft, cybercrimes, cyber scams and other n numbers of its malicious applications. Any state can be easily bullied and targeted by its malicious applications, therefore in order to extract the benefits of AI in different sectors, and to avoid its harms, it is importance to effectively balance AI with its proper potential. Today you can't ignore AI, you have to be capable enough to address it's bullying on your national assets indigenously that too well on time, before it get too late. No matter whether you are using AI to ease your people or your industry or not, you have to be resilient enough to address its bad effects at least on your economy, otherwise your economy will go back a decade or two in terms of progress, shattering all your economic dreams and targets. Hence underestimating Artificial Intelligence will not less than a blunder for any nation today.

3.2 Role of Information Technology

The IT sector of India which is a cluster of computers, software's and telecommunications is growing in leap and bouncy manner. India has an impressive position worldwide because of its IT industry. IT based services are vital for increasing productivity and economic growth. The IT companies have increased their

contribution to India's GDP from 1.2% in 1998 to almost 8% in 2018. The IT and BPM (Business Process Management) industry together have greater than 4.5 million workers as FY21. India is expected to have a digital economy of \$ 1 Trillion by 2025. There are endless opportunities in Information Technology in the form of digital targeted marketing, E-Commerce, digital communication, data sharing, enhancing business, products and services reach via websites, portals and online social media channels and platforms. India is also a global leader in providing IT services to global companies. India is also a home to vibrant IT start-up ecosystems.

3.3 Role of Data Management

Data is a crucial input for the development of any nation. Data deprivation cause poor policy planning, poor policy implementation and as a result poor growth in economic sense. Data is not only needed to address the policy making requirements, but also for the formulation of decisions, rolling out of new schemes, drafting of new plan of action. Data is crucial to manage climate risk, strategy making as per the market trends, floating information to the audience for respective subject matters. Today no nation in the world can afford running governance in parallel in the milieu of data divide and data deprivation. Nation's data is a crucial and confidential subject matter which can play a crucial role in the economic success of the nation as a whole.

Data is generated in large volumes from multiple sources, which it generally called as big data. Today, it become mandatory for all the nation's to keep a maximum control on the data, which is being generated and circulated within the national boundaries of their country. Data leaks and data theft are also becoming as a national issues of emergency. Your data is worth enough to provide you a snapshot of the kind of demography you have inside your borders. The data can exactly tell you about the business strength, economic figures, GDP numbers, and demand of the population, industry trends, supply system and nation's socio-economic condition. Data is like a biggest treasure of the digital world order. Big companies, start-ups, industry tycoons as well as government bodies rely on these data figures to write their respective saga of economic growth and success.

Also the creation of 'targeted development action plan' is only possible with the help of data. Until and unless, we had the adequate availability of data; of the economy we are actually governing, we can't make requisite improvements in the areas we are lagging behind. If we really want to break the vicious cycle of our stagnant growth or negligible growth of an underperforming sector, it is important to have all the sufficient data into our hand.

The report, titled 'Cost of a Data Breach', by IBM and Ponemon Research Institute, was based on real-world data breaches experienced by 550 organizations globally between March 2021 and March 2022, showed that Indian firms lost a whopping ₹176 million on an average in financial year 2021-22 to data breaches, a 25% increase from ₹140 million in FY20, and up 6.6% from ₹165 million in FY21. The IBM report finding 83% of organizations experiencing more than one data breach in their lifetime globally. Data breach is not a small problem to be ignored easily. Rather data breach incidences will take a jump even with a faster pace, because data is becoming a common substance for every business and economy. Data access can transfer our economic opportunity in someone's others hand. The policy makers must therefore be practical about data management and must harness the best possible use of data for unfolding the economic success, otherwise you will lose your precious financial assets in all these data breach and data theft cases. Data management is one of the crucial aspect to unlock economic success of any nation.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Artificial Intelligence as an Important Factor of Sustainable and Crisis-Free Economic Growth, (Rafael Abdulov). The introduction of Artificial Intelligence based on AI, can be helpful in crisis free growth of the economy as a whole. The economic benefit is not only limited to the individual companies, but also to the scale of entire economy.

Hammer, A. and Karmakar, S. (2021), "Automation, AI and the future of Work in India" Employee Relations, Vol. 43 No. 6, pp. 1327–1341. The research paper specifically highlighted the fact that the application of AI will occur in niches specifically in the manufacturing and the service sector will bring back enormous amount of employment opportunities, as a result there are chances for the adequate addressing of societal inequalities in the nation. In the nutshell, AI is the powerful technology of tomorrow, and with its potentials to revolutionize the way the industries work with much improvement will directly help in raising economic progress of the nation.

T. Dhanabalan, A. Sathish, Transforming Indian Industries Through Artificial Intelligence and Robotics in Industry 4.0., A lot of AI powered technologies has been developed which aimed to improve the economy as well as the quality of life. AI can drive the GDP growth. The research paper also highlighted the relevance of AI in different sectors and industries. The present scenario of AI start-ups in India as well as the policy planning priorities for the future. India can use AI in solving some of its biggest problems, particularly in healthcare and education. AI can considerably improve the economic growth of the nation as well. Government has a major role to play in promoting the AI via extensive Research and Development. At the same time, we need to update the workforce with the new age employability options of AI, IT and Data Management.

Singh, Nirvikar (2014): Information Technology and its role in India's economic development: A review, Working Paper, No. 718, University of California, Economics Department, Santa Cruz, CA according to their study in the research paper, Information Technology have the capacity to increase the efficiency of both government and private provision. Information Technology can also play a stellar role in increase the reach of governance to the people via e-governance. Not only this, IT can also improve rural communications, enhance e-commerce, manufacturing and improve transparency in public delivery system. Today investment in the information technologies can give you enormous opportunities to gain economic prowess in every sector. The research paper consider that IT is ultimately just a tool, but it is inherently powerful and extremely versatile. IT can enhance many aspects of the Indian economy and the lives of ordinary people in countless ways.

Information and Communication Technology and Economic Growth in India, (Abdul A. Erumban, Deb Kusum Das). This research paper evaluate the impact of ICT i.e. Information and Communication Technology on economic growth. It help improve productivity, gain efficiency and faster growth. The paper highlight the importance of investment in ICT as well as its application in several sectors, not only in the service sector. Only then it will be able to provide its benefits to the entire economy as a whole. Not only this, there are several indirect benefits studied and considered, if a nation in particular made investment in ICT. Such technologies are a push factor for the national growth in every sector of the economy. Therefore we can't underestimate the potential of ICT to unlock our businesses success stories.

Evaluating India's Economic Growth: Challenges and Opportunities on the Path to 5 Trillion Dollars (Dr. A.Shaji George, 2023). As per the stated research paper, India has tremendous opportunities to grow and obtain economic gains, India currently is blessed with the demographic dividend as well and can yield new

heights so desired. But for obtaining all the aspirational goals, we need to make structural changes in policy making, close Centre–State coordination etc. Harnessing technology across governance to improve service delivery should be prioritized. The economic progress is a holistic approach, which can be achieved with the combination of all in total. From technology to taxation to investment to governance, the world is watching the way India will chase its economic targets.

5. ADVANTAGES TO INDIA ON EFFECTIVE HARNESSING THE TECHNICAL POTENTIAL OF AI, IT & DATA MANAGEMENT

There are endless sectoral benefits to the nation, if we are able to effectively harness the potential of Artificial Intelligence, Information Technology as well as the Data Management. Better is to concentrate on the stated benefits individually of each of such technology in order to realize their real potential.

5.1 Benefits of AI i.e. Artificial Intelligence

1. AI has the potential to revolutionize the healthcare sector in the form of virtual nurses, easy data entry, easy fixing of appointment with a doctor, easy analyzing of test reports etc.
2. AI will give a push to employment opportunities.
3. AI can help less experienced workers in enhancing their productivity much faster.
4. AI can also improve your output generation capacity. You will be able to produce more number of output per day and will be able to get good return as revenue.
5. According to a study by Bank of America, Global revenue associated with AI software, hardware, service and sales will likely grow at 19% per year, reaching \$900 billion by 2026, compared to \$ 318 billion in 202017. (Reference in Point 17).
6. AI powered solutions help businesses to respond to customer grievances and queries more efficiently¹⁸.
7. AI also ensure 24-hour service availability and delivers the same consistency and quality performance any time you use it.
8. AI can saves millions of dollar of a nation, by effectively adhering its benefits in disaster management.
9. AI help to detect and prevent cyber fraud and hacks to a certain extent.
10. According to a report by McKinsey Global Institution, AI has the potential to add up to \$ 13 trillion to the global economy by the year 2030.

5.2 Benefits of IT i.e. Information Technology

1. IT sector can push more e-commerce start-ups in the coming days in India.
2. With robust IT infrastructure in place, every Indian can enjoy improved connectivity and better services.
3. We can have faster communication services.

4. We can do a lot of our physical activities online, at our comfort pace like shopping, payment, filing complaints, return and refund etc.
5. Robust IT infrastructure with minimum loops & leakages, can help you to detect cybercrime and cyber-attacks in real time with suggestive measures to keep everything save, without any risk.
6. Improved software and systems like ERP, CRM etc, will help enhance the productivity of the businesses leading them to earn higher revenue.

5.3 Benefits of Data Management

1. Data Management help to keep the data generated by India under the legitimate control of India.
2. Managing & storing the demographic data of the Indians, will help the government to frame adequate policy measures of its people.
3. Data Management means controlling and safeguarding the data as well. Which means we can keep our data safe and secure from the third party.
4. Data Management include data upgradation as well, today India hold enormous data in the form of UIDAI Aadhar, Umang App, CoWin registration and other online application channels.
5. The government will be able to take better data-driven decisions.

6. DISADVANTAGES FOR NOT HARNESSING THE TECHNICAL POTENTIAL OF THE TECH TRIO I.E. (ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE, INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY AND DATA MANAGEMENT SYSTEMS)

However ignorance of technology as a whole can be a major weakness for any nation, if that nation is actually aspirational about some of the major economic targets like what India have i.e. to become a \$ 5 Trillion Economy by 2027. Therefore, you have to be a tech-friendly country, with maximum utilization of technology in each and every sector. Since the area of technology is so vast that it is not possible for us to cover each and every type of technology. Therefore, for the purpose of convenience, this research paper includes only three technology heads - Artificial Intelligence, Information Technology and Data Management systems. And we have simultaneously discuss the disadvantages for not utilizing their technical potential adequately.

There can be countless disadvantages for not effectively utilizing the technical potential of the aforesaid trio of (Artificial Intelligence, Information Technology and Data Management systems). Also, these losses are not in one particular sector or to one particular community. Rather the disadvantages can supposed to be fatal for the entire economy as a whole. In fact, underestimating the technical potential could slow down our economic growth compared to other economies, who are utilizing similar technology in its every facet and form. The following are some of the disadvantages that have been observed as a consequence of ignoring the technical potential of AI, IT as well as Data Management. These are stated as below:-

1. According to a report published in The Hindu Newspaper dated January 8th, 2024, in their "Text & Context" section article titled "How voice cloning through Artificial Intelligence is being used for scams" reveals that 47% of the surveyed Indians have either been a victim or knew someone who had fallen prey to an AI generated voice scam. The number of victims in India are almost twice the global average. Anyone of us, can become the possible victim of such AI generated voice scams

anytime. We simply can become victimized just because of the fact that we had under estimated the potential of AI and its ill application via some destructive segment of the society.

2. There has been State sponsored cyber espionage attempts particularly from China, on India's critical infrastructure like cyber-attack on servers of the All India Institute of Medical Sciences (AIIMS) in 2022, cyber-attack on Indian power grid assets and other sensitive sectors such as defence and finance. These repeated cyber espionage and cyber-attack incidences disclosure our technological fragility and our failure to handled them at the right time, because of our under estimation of their potential.
3. CERT-In (The Indian Computer Emergency Response Team); India's nodal agency to deal with cyber security threats, which comes under the Ministry of Electronics and Information Technology (MeitY) has tackled over 1.39 million cyber security incidents in 2022 as per the data from their annual report. These figures will doubled and tripled in the years to come ahead, as cyber world is the future of tomorrow, and not everyone using technology is making its ethical utilization. Therefore it is the responsibility of the state to consider these figures and put adequate majors in actions and policies vis-à-vis these Information Technology potential to effectively counter such cyber threats.
4. A study by an IIT-Kanpur based incubated start-up confirmed that financial frauds accounted for 75% of the cybercrimes in India from Jan 2020 to Jun 2023. These cybercrimes are the one sucking hard earn money of the innocent people in the form of ransom, just by using their smart minds. We can definitely prevent these increased cybercrimes, if we implement right information technology measures as a part of our defensive system.
5. We all know the fact that "Data is the new oil". A nation which is not doing its data management today on its own, is actually losing the real assets of their nation. The absence of adequate and reliable data management system domestically, passes the technical power in the hands of other state actors to misuse this information to fulfill their selfish interest.
6. Data hacking incidences is also a challenge. For instance, in Feb 2021, hackers broke the database of Air India, and steal the information of nearly 4.5 million Air India airlines customers. We can avoid such hacking cases only, when we will have Anti-hacking technology in place.

The above discussed points are enough to reveal the fact that Technology can't be taken into granted in its any facet. Therefore, it is quintessential for any nation to not only harness technical potential because of its boons which can lead to economic success, but also for the fact that this similar technological potential can act as a emancipator tool to rescue nation's from these technological disasters such as cyber frauds, cyber-attacks, cybercrimes and data thefts. Just like diamond cuts diamond, similarly the technical potential has the equivalent power to safeguard nations from this technical menace, so created by Artificial Intelligence, Informational Technology and Data Management.

7. LIMITATION OF THE STUDY

It is not possible to cover the technology in its holistic sense to depict how much it is crucial for the economic success of any nation, especially for the case of India. As a result, there are some confinement in our study as well. With this research paper, we try our best possible to cover all the three aspect of technology in the best possible manner, but still there remain some of the limitation and these are as stated below:-

1. The research paper is based on secondary data, and lack equivalent authenticity what it should possess, if it will be based on primary data.
2. The scope of the study is just limited towards only three form i.e. Artificial intelligence, information technology and data management. However, Technology had so many forms in it. For instance machine learning, big data, cloud computing, deep learning, robotics, Internet of things, Digital twin technology etc.
3. The research paper only highlight the positive and negative side of effectively utilizing or harnessing the technical potential of the Artificial intelligence, information technology and data management. It did not suggest the appropriate path of using the tech trio for immediate and long lasting economic success.
4. The research paper only focuses on technology track; that too specific about AI, IT & Data Management. However, technology is just a single part of the whole economy. The paper lack its appropriate inter-relation with other sector for economic success.
5. No doubt that all three of these technologies are the future of modern economies, but India still have mile to go, as we lack concrete initiatives & policy making.

8. CONCLUSION

There is no doubt that technologies are the future of modern economies, therefore it is quintessential for any nation to not only harness technical potential because of its boons but to also rescue nation's from the technological disasters of the time. Things are changing so frequently, that we need technological proficient workforce who are able enough to harness the technical potential of all these technology i.e. AI, IT and Data Management. New India need technical professions how are smart enough to put these technologies for the economic benefit of the nation. Although it is a long process, and demand drastic improvement in our approach to use technology for India's economic development. India need to frame effective policies for the right utilization of these technological factors. We also have to set our priorities, goals and economic target vis-à-vis AI, IT and Data Management.

The Indian government must also put in place, respective plan of action for AI, IT and Data Management with strict legal measures to avoid any potential misuse & future economic loss. The government also need to promote AI start-ups, IT reach and localization of data with due respect towards citizen's data privacy. Fortunately India is blessed with the demographic dividend, and government must channelize this demographic dividend with right tech-skills, so that future workforce can use these tech domains for establishing their career and writing nation's economic success story.

- India need to make India specific Plan of Action for AI, IT and Data Management with specific targets sector-wise, so that we can harness the boons of the aforesaid technologies at the right time.
- India must skill the human resource, by inculcating AI, IT & Data Management as career domain in the education system.
- India need to have proper law or act on AI, IT & Data Management with clearly stated boundaries on free use and restricted use. The amount of punishment & legal procedure in case of misuse.
- India also need to frame policies for international collaboration in the fields of AI, IT & Data Management.

- India also need to set-up AI, IT & Data Management labs or centers in major cities, where people can take up training or short term courses about these technologies to fit and upgrade themselves with the changed job design.
- We need to make AI Committees in the Government's ministry itself, so that the committee can release AI related rules & regulation from time to time for the welfare of the nation.
- The government also need to enhance the funding on Research and Development for AI, IT and Data Management, so that we can successfully use them in multiple sector.

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